

Neural Surrogate HMC: Accelerated Hamiltonian Monte Carlo with a Neural Network Surrogate Likelihood

Linnea M. Wolniewicz^{*1}, Peter Sadowski¹, Claudio Corti^{2,3}

¹*Information and Computer Sciences, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, 1680 East-West Road, Honolulu HI, USA*

²*Physics and Astronomy, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, 2505 Correa Road, Honolulu HI, USA*

³*NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, 8800 Greenbelt Road, Greenbelt MD, USA*

Bayesian Inference with Markov Chain Monte Carlo requires efficient computation of the likelihood function. In some scientific applications, the likelihood must be computed by numerically solving a partial differential equation, which can be prohibitively expensive. We demonstrate that some such problems can be made tractable by amortizing the computation with a surrogate likelihood function implemented by a neural network. We show that this has two additional benefits: reducing noise in the likelihood evaluations and providing fast gradient calculations. In experiments, the approach is applied to a model of heliospheric transport of galactic cosmic rays, where it enables efficient sampling from the posterior of latent parameters in the Parker equation.

1 Introduction

Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods are widely used to perform Bayesian inference in the sciences, but the computations can be prohibitively expensive. Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) [1, 2] is an approach to accelerate MCMC sampling: compared to traditional MCMC methods, such as Random-Walk Metropolis-Hastings (RWMH) [3], HMC provides faster convergence to the target distribution and lower autocorrelation between samples. However, HMC requires the likelihood function to be both tractable and differentiable. In this work, we address a scenario in which the likelihood function is calculated by numerically solving a partial differential equation (PDE), making it incompatible with HMC for three reasons: it is non-differentiable, it is too slow, and it suffers from numerical instabilities. Our solution is to train a neural network (NN) surrogate likelihood that solves all three of these problems.

Previous work has used surrogate models to speed up HMC sampling. HMC accelerates convergence by using the gradient at each step to take steps towards high-likelihood samples [4], but the computations of

the likelihood function and its gradient can still be prohibitively expensive. This has motivated the use of fast approximations, such as using a Gaussian process surrogate of the likelihood [5] or an extreme learning machine surrogate [6]. Other work has used NNs to approximate the gradient of the likelihood [7], predict the HMC transition kernel [8], and provide a trainable kernel within the dynamic update of the HMC [9]. Foreman, Jin & Osborn [10] proposed the use of NNs to replace consecutive leapfrog steps. Dhulipala, Che & Shields [11] applied Hamiltonian NNs to learn the Hamiltonian dynamics of an HMC sampler and continue sampling without gradient information. Our setup differs in that the original likelihood function can only be queried imperfectly by a numerical solver, and is thus never used for the HMC rejection step — the surrogate model is assumed to provide a more reliable prediction of the likelihood function and is thus used throughout HMC sampling. To the best of our knowledge, no work has explored the use of NNs as a surrogate likelihood function in this way.

In experiments, we demonstrate our approach by applying it to the problem of modeling the heliospheric transport of galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) [12, 13], a component of space weather that will influence the scheduling of future crewed space missions. The likelihood function computed by the numerical solver fails a fraction of the time due to numerical instabilities, resulting in a noisy estimate of the true likelihood. A NN surrogate model — with an inductive bias towards smoothness — is trained on a large dataset of precomputed PDE solutions. This provides significant improvement in both accuracy and computational cost per likelihood evaluation during MCMC. It also means the surrogate likelihood is differentiable, which enables the use of HMC. Using this approach, we obtain state-of-the-art constraints on the global heliospheric transport parameters.

*Corresponding author. E-Mail: linneamw@hawaii.edu

Figure 1: The NN (top left) takes as input eight latent parameters of the heliosphere and predicts the GCR flux at 1 AU for 32 rigidity steps. These steps are uniformly distributed in logspace between 0.2 and 200 GV. The NN is trained with targets from a numerical solver that suffers from instabilities (top right), and a surrogate likelihood is computed by comparing the NN outputs with observed fluxes (bottom left). This surrogate likelihood is used to sample from the posterior (bottom right) using HMC.

2 Constraining the global heliospheric transport of GCRs

We demonstrate our method by using it to constrain five parameters characterizing the transport of GCRs within the heliosphere based on observations by detectors in low Earth orbit (1 AU). GCRs constitute a major radiation hazard for deep-space human exploration, and understanding their behavior will be critical for crewed missions to Mars and beyond.

2.1 Problem set-up

The transport of GCRs within the heliosphere is described by the Parker equation [14]:

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{V}_{sw} \cdot \nabla J + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K} \nabla J) + \frac{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{V}_{sw}}{3} \beta R^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left(\frac{J}{\beta R^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $J(\mathbf{r}, R)$ is the measured GCR flux at a given position, \mathbf{r} , and rigidity, $R = (\text{particle momentum}) / (\text{particle charge})$, while β is the particle speed divided by the speed of light. The various terms represent the interactions of GCRs with the solar wind, a plasma ejected by the Sun moving with velocity \mathbf{V}_{sw} , and the heliospheric magnetic field (HMF).

The HMF is characterized by the intensity at 1 AU, I_{HMF} , the solar dipole tilt angle, α , and by the direction (positive or negative polarity). The diffusion tensor, \mathbf{K} , describes the GCR scattering and drifting due to HMF small and large-scale structures. It is charac-

terized by a normalization constant, k_{\parallel}^0 , and by the rigidity slopes of the diffusion coefficient (DC) in the directions parallel ($a_{\parallel}, b_{\parallel}$) and perpendicular (a_{\perp}, b_{\perp}) to the HMF.

Observations come from the PAMELA¹ and AMS-02² instruments. PAMELA measured H fluxes at a monthly cadence between 0.4-50 GV in the period 2006-2014 [15, 16], and AMS-02 measured H fluxes at daily cadence between 1-100 GV in the period 2011-2019 [17]. Our model parameters are those used to describe the HMF conditions in [18].

Our complete methodology is visualized in Figure 1. We first train a NN to take in eight parameters characterizing the transport of GCRs within the heliosphere and predict the GCR flux at 1 AU for 32 rigidity steps uniformly distributed in logspace between 0.2 and 200 GV. This process is shown in the top panel of the Figure 1. After training, the NN is used as a surrogate likelihood function to sample from the posterior distribution of five latent parameters of the heliosphere with HMC. The likelihood of a set of sampled parameters is computed using the equation shown in the bottom left panel of Figure 1. The sampled parameters are passed through the NN (along with three other parameters specified in Section 2.3) and the predicted GCR flux is compared with observed fluxes to determine the likelihood of the set of sampled parameters. After many steps, our method provides posterior PDFs for the five latent parameters of the heliosphere sampled by HMC and posterior PDFs on the predicted GCR fluxes.

2.2 Surrogate neural network

The likelihood function requires solving the Parker equation for a given set of parameters to predict the flux of GCRs at different rigidities. This is slow, and solving the Parker equation for slightly different parameters during MCMC is inefficient as we expect the solution to vary smoothly. We create a fast surrogate of the likelihood function by training a NN that predicts the GCR fluxes for any given parameters. This NN has an inductive bias towards smoothness, can be evaluated quickly at inference time, and is differentiable. This conveniently solves all three obstacles to the use of HMC for Bayesian inference.

To train the NN surrogate, numerical solutions were computed for almost three million parameter values, similar to what was done in [18]. This large initial computational cost is embarrassingly paralleliz-

¹PAMELA monthly protons are available at the ASI Cosmic Ray Database: <https://tools.ssd.cnr.it/CosmicRays/>

²AMS-02 daily protons are available at: <https://ams02.space/sites/default/files/publication/202105/table-s1-s2824.csv>

able. Solutions that demonstrated numerical instability were removed, resulting in 1,987,658 negative HMF polarity samples, which were further split into training sets (90%) and test sets (10%) with the latter used for early stopping (monitored test loss) and hyperparameter optimization.

The surrogate NN consists of a fully connected network with two hidden layers of 256 units each and SELU activations, 8 inputs, and 32 outputs. It predicts the modulated flux at 32 rigidity steps, uniformly distributed in logspace between 0.2 and 200 GV, from the 8 input parameters (tilt angle α , HMF intensity at Earth I_{HMF} , solar wind speed V_{sw} , and parameters related to the parallel and perpendicular diffusion coefficients, k_{\parallel}^0 , a_{\parallel} , b_{\parallel} , a_{\perp} , and b_{\perp}). It is trained to minimize the mean absolute error using the Adam [19] optimizer with the ReduceLROnPlateau learning rate schedule (initial learning rate $1e-4$) and a batch size of 128. L2 regularization is used to prevent overfitting (weight $1e-6$).

The relative error of the NN predictions compared to the numerically stable model solutions was found to be very low — between 1% and 2% at all rigidities — with no significant correlations with the input values. Thus, we conclude that the NN is an accurate approximation of the numerical model within the parameter space domain used for training and testing.

2.3 MCMC

The observational data consists of 132 different time intervals of interest, and we infer the model parameters separately for each interval. HMC is performed using the No-U-Turn Sampler [20] and the Dual Averaging Step Size Adaptation kernel of the TensorFlow Probability MCMC package to generate 10^5 samples from the posterior for each time interval. Additionally, we apply thinning by only selecting every 100th sample and discarding the first 100,000 samples as part of the burn-in process.

The five sampled model parameters are k_{\parallel}^0 , a_{\parallel} , b_{\parallel} , a_{\perp} , and b_{\perp} . The tilt angle, the HMF intensity on Earth and the solar wind speed (α , I_{HMF} , and V_{SW}) are fixed to their 1-year backward average for each interval, using data from NASA/GSFC's OMNI daily dataset [21] through OMNIWeb³ and the Wilcox Solar Observatory⁴.

The likelihood of a sampled parameter \mathbf{z} is determined by summing the standard chi-squared between the GCR fluxes predicted by the model ($\hat{\mathbf{x}} = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{z})$) and the observed GCR flux (\mathbf{x}) over the 32 rigidity steps predicted by the NN:

³<https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

⁴<http://wso.stanford.edu/Tilts.html>

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}) = \exp\left(\frac{-\chi^2(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\mathbf{x}})}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

The likelihood function is selected because it assigns high likelihood to low χ^2 values and low likelihood to high χ^2 values. It should be noted that using a surrogate NN induces a significant bias towards likelihood smoothness, which suits our application but may not be generally applicable.

The NN is trained on data from a limited domain of parameter space and so should not be expected to generalize well outside this domain. We prevent the HMC from sampling outside the “trusted” domain with a prior distribution, $p(z)$. This prior is uniform in the domain of the training data (with a value of $1e6$) and rapidly decays in every direction outside the domain.

For comparison, we also generate samples over each time interval with the no-gradient RWMH [3]. The scale of the normally distributed perturbations during RWMH was manually set to $1e-2$ to achieve an acceptance ratio close to 25%. We do not use thinning for RWMH and again discard the first 100,000 samples as part of the burn-in process.

3 Results

The surrogate NN is trained on a grid of 10^6 likelihood evaluations and is then used to generate 10^5 samples from the posterior. Figure 2 shows that RWMH samples need to be thinned by a factor of 10^2 to achieve the same autocorrelation as HMC, so obtaining 10^5 uncorrelated samples with RWMH for a single experiment would require at least 10^7 likelihood evaluations. This is already a factor of ten more computations than our NN approach, but considering that the trained surrogate NN can be reused for all 132 time intervals, the savings become three orders of magnitudes. Furthermore, the speedup from the NN is immense: on a 1-core CPU the likelihood evaluation takes $\approx 5m50s$ [18] and often fails due to numerical instabilities, whereas the surrogate NN is stable and has an inference time of $\approx 21ms$.

The probability distribution functions (PDFs) of the free parameters obtained with HMC for a single experiment are shown in Figure 3. The normalization of the DC (k_{\parallel}^0) and the slopes of the perpendicular DC (a_{\perp} and b_{\perp}) are well constrained by the data, as shown by their narrow PDFs. The slopes of the parallel DC (a_{\parallel} and b_{\parallel}) are less constrained, as expected, since perpendicular diffusion dominates the transport processes in the majority of the heliosphere. These results are in

Figure 2: Comparison of autocorrelation in HMC (top) and RWMH (bottom) samples k_{\parallel}^0 . Both HMC and RWMH samples shown were generated without thinning. The data used to compute the likelihood of samples were measured by PAMELA in the negative polarity time interval 2010/10/30-2010/11/26.

agreement with what was found in [18] using a grid-based ordinary least-square minimization procedure on the same AMS-02 data and numerical model. We improve on [18] by smoothing the numerical instabilities of the model and providing posterior PDFs for all free parameters of the numerical model and posterior PDFs on the predicted GCR fluxes.

4 Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of HMC using a NN surrogate likelihood. We have shown that this is a practical method that can be used to solve previously intractable problems. The potential problem that the NN surrogate should not be trusted outside the domain of the training data was identified and solved by penalizing samples outside this range. We additionally explored sampling with both HMC and RWMH and demonstrated the reduced computational cost the NN surrogate and HMC provide. This method provides state-of-the-art constraints on the heliospheric transport of galactic cosmic rays, and the resulting PDFs characterize the uncertainty on each transport parameter which enables better uncertainty estimates for GCR flux forecasts when planning future space missions. Neverthe-

Figure 3: 2D and 1D PDFs of the diffusion coefficient parameters obtained from the HMC for GCR flux measured by AMS-02 in the negative polarity time interval 2013/02/21-2013/03/19. The top right panel shows a comparison of the maximum likelihood NN model (red line) with observations, together with the 68% and 95% credible intervals. The black cross shows the parameter values corresponding to the maximum likelihood in the 5D PDF. The magenta star and the orange line show the 1D average and maximum over each parameter, respectively. The blue dashed line shows the 1D 68.3% credible interval, and the green area shows the 2D 95.4% credible interval.

less, we recognize that our method’s applicability may not extend to all problem domains, given that it assumes the NN surrogate accurately learns the likelihood function.

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